

Dielectric, Ferroelectric, and Piezoelectric Properties of Ca²⁺/ Sn⁴⁺ modified (Ba_{0.97}Ca_{0.03}Ti_{0.97}Sn_{0.03})O₃ Lead-Free Electroceramic

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Abstract

BaTiO₃ based lead-free electroceramic modified by Ca²⁺/Sn⁴⁺ i.e. Ba_{0.97}Ca_{0.03}Ti_{0.97}Sn_{0.03}O₃ was synthesized using solid-state reaction method; investigated dielectric, ferroelectric and piezoelectric properties. The structural analysis shows that the formation of perovskite structure with tetragonal crystal lattice symmetry having *P4mm* space group. The microstructural observation reveals the dense microstructure having defined grain boundaries to grains with an average grain size ~ 38μm and the relative density of ~ 98 %. The temperature dependent dielectric measurements reveal the dielectric maxima i.e. Curie temperature (*T_C*) at 115 °C having dielectric constant $\epsilon_r \sim 12857$. The ferroelectric nature of the sample was confirmed from the electric field induced polarization-electric field (P-E) hysteresis loop measurement having $P_r = 5.19 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, $E_c = 2.14 \text{ kV}/\text{cm}$. The poled Ba_{0.97}Ca_{0.03}Ti_{0.97}Sn_{0.03}O₃ exhibit the piezoelectric charge coefficient of 280 pC/N. The present study gives an insight on the stabilization of *T_C* for BaTiO₃ based lead-free ceramics by Ca²⁺ and Sn⁴⁺ modification.

Keywords – Lead-free piezoelectric, BaTiO₃, Dielectric constant, piezoelectric coefficient.